

FEATURES OF PREGNANCY-RELATED OSTEOPOROSIS IN UZBEK POPULATION

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Abstract. *This article presents data on the features of the etiology, pathogenesis, clinical picture, diagnosis and treatment of osteoporosis associated with pregnancy and lactation (PLO) in women of reproductive age.*

Knowledge of the clinical manifestations will facilitate early diagnosis, which is critical for timely treatment in the presence of metabolic bone disorders. Since the best approaches to treating women with (PLO) have not yet been determined, further research into this condition is therefore needed.

Keywords: *bone mineral density, osteoporosis, pregnancy, lactation.*

Pregnancy and lactation-associated osteoporosis (PLO) is a type of osteoporosis that occurs in women with normal bone structure during late pregnancy or the lactation period. It is a rare and poorly understood condition. The incidence of PLO is approximately 0.4 per 100,000 women; however, the true prevalence of the disease remains undetermined, as a significant number of patients remain undiagnosed [4; 5; 8].

Hadji P. et al. [2] found that 88.0% of patients with PLO suffered from one or more fractures, with an average of 3.3 fractures per patient. The most common fracture site was the thoracolumbar spine, with fractures of Th11, Th12, L1, and L2 occurring in 29.0%, 37.0%, 48.0%, and 35% of cases, respectively. Additionally, women with PLO more frequently experienced dental problems in childhood ($p < 0.001$) and were less likely to engage in sports both before ($p < 0.002$) and after puberty ($p < 0.01$). The same study also found that women with PLO had severe illnesses during pregnancy twice as often as the control group ($p < 0.029$), which increased the frequency of their immobilization ($p < 0.005$).

In another study, Hadji P. et al. [3] examined transient osteoporosis of the hip (TOH) associated with pregnancy and found that 12.1% of patients with TOH suffered from hip fractures, and 90.9% complained of hip pain ($p \leq 0.001$). There was also a significant increase in the risk of TOH in patients with dental problems in childhood (OR 3.7; 95% CI 1.3–10.7) and in patients with a lack of physical activity in childhood (OR 4.2; 95% CI 1.3–12.9).

In a retrospective, cross-sectional, and descriptive study conducted by Tuna F. et al. [12], 60.6% of patients had fractures in the thoracic region, 30.3% in the lumbar region, and 9.1% in the sacral region. An optimal vitamin D level during pregnancy was observed in 14.3% of patients, with 64.3% showing a deficiency of the micronutrient, and 21.4% having insufficient vitamin D levels. Osteoporosis was predominantly localized in trabecular bone (L1-L4; Z-score -2.9, femur; Z-score -2.19).

Objective: The aim of this study was to examine the clinical and anamnestic data, biochemical markers of bone remodeling, and bone mineral density (BMD) indicators in women with pregnancy and lactation-associated osteoporosis (PLO).

Materials and methods:

To achieve the objectives of the study, we formed two groups of subjects. The first, main group consisted of 27 women diagnosed with PLO who attended the clinic at the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Endocrinology (RSSPMCE) from 2020 to 2024. These women experienced back pain during pregnancy and/or lactation, and MRI revealed compression fractures of the vertebrae at various locations. The second, control group consisted of 14 women without fractures and without a history of back pain. The groups were comparable in age (PLO group - 30.1 ± 5.7 years, control group - 30.9 ± 6.5 years).

Inclusion criteria: the presence of low-trauma fractures either during pregnancy or in the immediate postpartum period.

Exclusion criteria: the presence of secondary osteoporotic conditions (such as hyperparathyroidism, Cushing's syndrome, and hyperthyroidism).

For each subject, a standardized questionnaire was completed, developed by specialists at the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Endocrinology, Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The questionnaire included passport data, osteoporosis risk factors, and laboratory data.

Laboratory biochemical studies included the determination of total calcium, phosphorus, alkaline phosphatase, and parathyroid hormone (PTH) levels in the blood, vitamin D (25(OH)D), as well as biochemical markers of bone remodeling— β -CrossLaps, osteocalcin, and PICP.

BMD was measured using dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry (GE Lunar Corporation, Prodigy system) in the lumbar region (L1-L4) and both hips. Radiographic fractures were further characterized using MRI. Data regarding pregnancy and the type and duration of treatment received were also reviewed.

Statistical analysis of the results was performed using Microsoft Excel and IBM SPSS Statistics 23 software. Baseline data were assessed for normal distribution compliance using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Results

Our comparative analysis showed that women in the control and main groups were comparable in clinical indicators. The BMI in the PLO group was 23.6 ± 3.9 kg/m², compared to 24.59 ± 4.5 kg/m² in the control group ($p=0.45$). The age at menarche (PLO - 12.9 ± 1.2 years; control - 13.2 ± 1.42 years; $p=0.50$), number of pregnancies (PLO - 2.7 ± 2.0 ; control - 2.8 ± 1.9 ; $p=0.86$), number of deliveries (PLO - 1.9 ± 1.2 ; control - 2.2 ± 1.3 ; $p=0.48$), interpregnancy interval, and breastfeeding duration were also similar between the groups.

All patients sought help due to complaints of pain in the lumbar-sacral region of the spine, with 13 (48.1%) experiencing pain during pregnancy and 14 (51.9%) reporting pain during lactation.

Bone fractures were predominantly observed during pregnancy and lactation. More than half (59.3%) of the patients experienced fractures during their first pregnancy, 2 (7.4%) women during their second pregnancy, 18.5% during their third pregnancy, and 1 (3.7%) patient during her fourth pregnancy. Three (11.1%) patients did not experience fractures (Figure 1a).

Figure 1. a. During which pregnancy the fractures occurred. b. Location of the fractures in the studied patients.

Regarding the location of the fractures, a significant portion was situated in the lumbar vertebrae (L1-L4) at 74.1%, more than half (55.6%) in the thoracic region (Th7-Th12), and 11.1% in the Th1-Th7 region. One patient presented with a fracture of the talar neck and regional osteoporosis of the foot bones. It is important to note that in the majority of cases (51.9%), multiple vertebral fractures were observed (Figure 1b).

Additionally, it should be emphasized that in 37.0% of cases, lumbar fractures were multiple (3-4 fractures), with an average of 3.7 fractures.

Analysis of the questionnaire data revealed that fractures in relatives were recorded only in the PLO group (14.8%). The frequency of dairy product consumption did not differ significantly between the groups (PLO – 48.1% versus 64.3% in the control group; OR 0.52; 95% CI 0.14-1.95; $p=0.33$). In the PLO group, 37.0% of participants did not regularly include dairy products in their diet, compared to 35.7% in the control group (OR 1.06; 95% CI 0.28-4.06; $p=0.93$) (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Frequency of osteoporosis risk factors.

In the PLO group, significantly fewer women led an active lifestyle (37.0% versus 85.7% in the control group; OR 0.10; 95% CI 0.02-0.53; $p=0.007$), and a higher proportion did not engage

in physical exercise (22.2% versus 14.3% in the control group; OR 1.71; 95% CI 0.30-9.87; $p=0.55$), with 40.7% performing physical activity irregularly.

It is well known that the synthesis of vitamin D in the body is influenced by various factors, including skin exposure. When asked whether they wear open clothing (outerwear with short sleeves and skirts not extending below the calves), significantly fewer patients with PLO (51.9% versus 92.9% in the control group; OR 0.08; 95% CI 0.01-0.73; $p=0.02$) responded affirmatively. According to our research, women in the control group were significantly more likely to consume coffee or carbonated drinks compared to patients with PLO (57.1% versus 7.4%; OR 0.06; 95% CI 0.01-0.36; $p=0.002$).

Phosphorus-calcium metabolism indicators and bone marker levels in both groups were within reference values.

Our analysis showed that 24 out of 27 women (88.9%) had fractures at various locations, with more than half (58.3%) experiencing multiple fractures.

The analysis revealed that in the lumbar spine (L1-L4), osteopenia was diagnosed in 7 (25.9%) and osteoporosis (OP) in 20 (74.1%) of the examined women, with the average Z-score and T-score being -2.84 ± 0.85 and -2.73 ± 1.12 , respectively; and BMD averaging 0.825 ± 0.12 g/cm².

Among the 20 women with lumbar spine OP, normal femoral BMD was observed in 5 (25.0%) patients, osteopenia in 11 (55.0%), and OP in 4 (20.0%) of the examined.

Additionally, the average Z-score, T-score, and BMD were as follows: left hip -1.58 ± 1.07 and -1.68 ± 0.98 ; 0.778 ± 0.12 g/cm²; right hip -1.63 ± 0.68 and -1.70 ± 0.78 ; 0.766 ± 0.09 g/cm².

Among the 24 patients with PLO, normal femoral neck BMD was observed in 7 (29.2%) of the examined women, osteopenia in 16 (66.7%), and osteoporosis (OP) in 1 (4.2%) woman. The average Z-score, T-score, and BMD values were as follows: left femoral neck - Z-score: -1.33 ± 0.84 , T-score: -1.44 ± 0.90 , BMD: 0.808 ± 0.11 g/cm²; right femoral neck - Z-score: -1.31 ± 0.56 , T-score: -1.28 ± 0.71 , BMD: 0.820 ± 0.09 g/cm².

Three women complained of back pain, and osteoporotic changes were detected in the L1-L4 region through radiodensitometry (Z-score: -3.13 ± 0.25 , T-score: -2.85 ± 0.35 , BMD: 0.860 ± 0.11 g/cm²) and osteopenia in the femoral bone (left femur: Z-score: -1.43 ± 0.21 , T-score: -1.23 ± 0.40 , BMD: 0.831 ± 0.08 g/cm²; right femur: Z-score: -1.50 , T-score: -1.50 , BMD: 0.762 g/cm²) and femoral neck (left femoral neck: Z-score: -1.33 ± 0.84 , T-score: -1.44 ± 0.90 , BMD: 0.808 ± 0.11 g/cm²; right femoral neck: Z-score: -1.31 ± 0.56 , T-score: -1.28 ± 0.71 , BMD: 0.820 ± 0.09 g/cm²); however, no vertebral fractures were detected on MRI.

Discussion

Pregnancy and lactation-associated osteoporosis (PLO) is a rare condition that has been described in numerous case reports in the literature since 1955. The pathological cause of PLO remains unclear, but endocrine, nutritional, genetic, and biomechanical factors have been suggested. Diagnosis is usually delayed, and the patient typically presents with pain due to a fragility fracture in the thoracolumbar spine or hip. The diagnostic approach for PLO is the same as for postmenopausal osteoporosis, using DEXA scanning. There is no consensus on the optimal treatment for PLO due to the lack of clinical trials.

A systematic review of 338 cases worldwide showed that the average age of patients with PLO was 35.7 years, and the mean body mass index was 22.2 kg/m². Ninety-two percent of patients

developed clinical symptoms within the period from 3 months before to 3 months after delivery [11].

In our study of 27 women with PLO and 14 women in the control group, the majority (74.1%) of fractures were localized in the L1-L4 vertebrae, more than half (55.6%) in the thoracic region (Th7-Th12), and 11.1% in the Th1-Th7 region, with an average of 3.7 ± 2.0 fractures. These findings are consistent with data from other authors: 3.9 [9], 3.3 [5], and 3.8 ± 2.0 [7].

We found that significantly fewer women with PLO led an active lifestyle (37.0% versus 85.7% in the control group; $p=0.007$), did not engage in physical exercise (22.2% versus 14.3% in the control group; $p=0.55$), and 40.7% performed physical activity irregularly.

According to Peltz-Sinvani N. et al. [9], significantly fewer women with PLO, compared to the control group, engaged in physical activity for more than 2 hours per week before pregnancy (37% vs. 67%, $p=0.015$) and during pregnancy (11% vs. 44%, $p=0.003$).

Kyvernitakis I. et al. [6], in a single-center prospective cohort study, investigated the risk of subsequent fractures in 107 patients with pregnancy and lactation-associated osteoporosis. During the observation period (6 years), 26 (24.3%) patients experienced a subsequent fracture. Overall, 30 (28.0%) patients reported a subsequent pregnancy, and among them, 6 (20.0%) reported a subsequent fracture. A significant correlation was found between the number of fractures at the time of diagnosis and the risk of subsequent fractures.

According to several researchers, due to the lack of awareness regarding the diagnosis and prognosis of PLO, some physicians even perform unnecessary surgical interventions, such as vertebroplasty, internal fixation, or hip replacement, leading to irreversible iatrogenic damage and a waste of medical resources [1; 10].

Therefore, it is crucial to promote the dissemination of knowledge and understanding of PLO among physicians in the fields of orthopedics, endocrinology, and obstetrics. However, there is currently limited information available on PLO.

A systematic review was conducted to study the risk factors, clinical manifestations, and treatment methods of this condition [11], but it should be noted that a comprehensive study on PLO is still lacking. This study describes the clinical features of 27 patients with PLO who were admitted to our clinic and aims to improve the understanding of this rare condition.

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